

Multi-Physics Simulations of Direct Lightning Damage to Elastoplastic Substrates

Jakob J. Schoser[#], Stephen Millmore[#], Nikolaos Nikiforakis[#]

[#]*Cavendish Laboratory, Department of Physics, University of Cambridge, United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland*

¹*jjjs71@cam.ac.uk*

²*stm31@cam.ac.uk*

³*nn10005@cam.ac.uk*

Abstract— In this work, we present a new method to holistically simulate the two-way interaction between a lightning arc and a damageable, elastoplastic substrate. This is achieved by solving a unified set of partial differential equations describing the coupled evolution of compressible fluids and solids under the influence of time-varying electromagnetic fields. This mathematical model is solved on a single computational grid using a shock-capturing finite volume method, where each material is modelled using its own, thermodynamically consistent equation of state, plasticity, and damage model. The model naturally captures material separation, which is important for the simulation of delamination and outgassing. To demonstrate the method, simulations of laboratory experiments are shown to capture the dynamics of the lightning plasma as well as thermal stresses and damage in the substrate.

Keywords— Lightning, MHD, Multiphysics, Numerical Simulation

I. ACRONYMS AND SYMBOLS

CFRP: Carbon fibre reinforced plastic

EOS: Equation of state

LSP: Lightning strike protection

MHD: Magnetohydrodynamics

PDE: Partial differential equation

\mathbf{A} : Magnetic vector potential [Tm]

\mathbf{B} : Magnetic field [T]

D : Damage [-]

\dot{D} : Damage rate [1/s]

E : Total energy [J/m³]

I : Electrical current [A]

\mathbf{J} : Electrical current density [A/m²]

S_R : Radiative source term [W/m³]

\mathbf{v} : Velocity [m/s]

$\bar{\mathbf{v}}^e$: Unimodular left stretch tensor [-]

α : Volume fraction [-]

ϵ_p : Plastic strain [-]

ρ : Density [kg/m³]

σ : Stress tensor [Pa]

σ_e : Electrical conductivity [S/m]

Φ : Plastic source term [1/s]

ϕ : Electric potential [V]

χ : Plastic strain rate [1/s]

II. INTRODUCTION

As new materials, fuels and aircraft configurations find their way into the aerospace sector, the state of the art in lightning strike protection (LSP) must be re-evaluated. Due to the large number of laboratory experiments required, developing new LSP and design tolerances is a time-consuming and costly process. Numerical simulations of lightning strike offer a low-cost alternative to experiments and have received increasing attention over the last decade. However, full simulation of the lightning strike phenomenon remains a challenge. This can be attributed to the complex damage mechanisms occurring in the substrate, as well as the difficulty of coupling the substrate model to a model for the lightning plasma. There is a large body of literature on simulations of direct lightning damage to carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRP), but most of these studies did not include a full magnetohydrodynamics (MHD) model the lightning plasma [1]. Rather, they used idealised loads to account for its presence. It has, however, been shown that capturing the correct plasma dynamics is crucial for accurate damage predictions [2]. Therefore, several authors developed models for the lightning plasma, usually based on the MHD approach [3]. Recent advances in the field were studies that include models for both the lightning plasma and the substrate material [4]. The work by Millmore and Nikiforakis [5] achieved strong two-way coupling between the lightning plasma and substrate material within a single code. They showed that the degradation of the substrate material's electrical conductivity significantly altered the dynamics of the plasma. However, they did not account for mechanical damage in the substrate. The aim of this work is to demonstrate a fully coupled, multi-physics simulation of the lightning plasma and substrate material that includes mechanical damage.

III. MATHEMATICAL MODEL

In this work, the combined dynamics of the lightning plasma and substrate material are captured by an Eulerian, unified

multi-physics model, which is based on previous work on damage and fracture due to detonations and impact [6]. The model tracks the volume fraction, density, plastic strain, and damage of each material separately, while assuming that velocity, pressure, and elastic deformation fields are shared between materials. It neglects the effects of viscosity and heat conduction, which are small over to the short time scales of interest. It should be noted that the method relies on continuum damage modelling, where damaged cells are not removed from the simulation, but the damage variable is instead used to locally reduce the stiffness of the material without any alteration to the computational mesh. The novelty of this work lies in the extension of the model to general equations of state (EOS), as well as the addition of terms for Joule heating, Lorentz force, and radiative losses, which are important for the lightning strike phenomenon. The model can be written as a system of non-linear, hyperbolic partial differential equations (PDEs):

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_k(\mathbf{U})}{\partial x_k} = \mathbf{S}_{noncons} + \mathbf{S}_{phys}$$

$$\mathbf{U} = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_{(l)} \\ (\alpha\rho)_{(l)} \\ (\alpha\rho\epsilon_p)_{(l)} \\ (\alpha\rho D)_{(l)} \\ \rho v_i \\ E \\ \bar{V}_{ij}^e \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{F}_k(\mathbf{U}) = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_{(l)} v_k \\ (\alpha\rho)_{(l)} v_k \\ (\alpha\rho\epsilon_p)_{(l)} v_k \\ (\alpha\rho D)_{(l)} v_k \\ \rho v_i v_k - \sigma_{ik} \\ E v_k - v_i \sigma_{ik} \\ \bar{V}_{ij}^e v_k - \bar{V}_{kj}^e v_i \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{S}_{noncons} = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_{(l)} \frac{\partial v_k}{\partial x_k} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{2}{3} \bar{V}_{ij}^e \frac{\partial v_k}{\partial x_k} - v_i \frac{\partial \bar{V}_{kj}^e}{\partial x_k} \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{S}_{phys} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ (\alpha\rho\chi)_{(l)} \\ (\alpha\rho\dot{D})_{(l)} \\ (\mathbf{J} \times \mathbf{B})_i \\ J_i/\sigma_e + v_i(\mathbf{J} \times \mathbf{B})_i - S_R \\ -\Phi_{ij} \end{pmatrix}$$

The current density and magnetic field are obtained from an electrostatic model involving the electric scalar potential and magnetic vector potential, following previous authors [3] [5].

$$\mathbf{J} = -\sigma_e \nabla \phi$$

$$\mathbf{B} = \nabla \times \mathbf{A}$$

$$\nabla(\sigma_e \nabla \phi) = 0$$

$$\nabla^2 \mathbf{A} = \mu_0 \mathbf{J}$$

To close the system of PDEs, constitutive relations are required for material properties. These are provided in the form of a thermodynamically consistent EOS, a plasticity model, and a damage model, along with a model for electrical conductivity and radiative cooling. For the lightning plasma, these relations are provided by a 19-species model of air plasma, which was specifically developed for lightning applications [7]. The radiative model follows the grey body approach [3]. The substrate material is assumed to obey an isotropic Romenskii EOS [8]. For metals, a Johnson-Cook plasticity model [9] is used along with a Bonora damage model [10]. For CFRP, as a proof of concept, the same approach is used. The mixture rules used to obtain the thermodynamic properties of cells containing multiple materials are detailed in [6].

IV. NUMERICAL METHOD

The evolution equations are solved using a shock-capturing, conservative finite volume method on a single Cartesian grid. Second-order accurate Strang splitting is used, allowing for the homogeneous, hyperbolic part of the equations to be treated in isolation at every time step. For this, the HLLD approximate Riemann solver [11] is used together with MUSCL reconstruction [12] to achieve second-order accuracy in space and time. For more information on Riemann solvers and shock-capturing finite volume schemes, the reader is referred to Toro [13]. The non-conservative source terms are rewritten as fluxes and included in the homogeneous update. The physical source terms, on the other hand, are integrated using the Dormand-Prince method [14]. The solution of the elliptic equations in the electrostatic model is achieved using a second-order accurate finite volume discretisation, which is solved using the direct LU solver from the PETSc library [9] at every time step.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To demonstrate the new method, a test case based on the experimental work of Sousa Martins [16] was investigated. In this experiment, a current waveform with a peak of 100 kA was applied to a 1 mm thick substrate via an indirect electrode. The problem was assumed to be axisymmetric, which allowed for all simulations to be performed in two dimensions in cylindrical coordinates. Furthermore, the electrical conductivities of undamaged aluminium and CFRP were taken as 32 MS/m and 16 kS/m, respectively. First, the models for the lightning plasma and the substrate material were tested separately, before they were combined in a fully coupled simulation that demonstrated the onset of direct lightning damage.

Figure 1: Density, pressure, and temperature within lightning plasma 10 μ s after attachment to rigid substrate with electrical conductivity of CFRP (left) and aluminium (right). The rigid substrate is shown in white.

A. *Lightning Plasma Model*

As a first step, the lightning plasma was considered with a rigid body approximation for the substrate material. For this, reflective boundary conditions were applied at the substrate surface. When solving for the electromagnetic fields, the electrical conductivity in the rigid body was set to the value of the material under investigation. The initial condition consisted of a cylindrical region of high-pressure plasma at 8000 K with a radius of 2 mm, surrounded by air at atmospheric conditions. The high-pressure region was required to provide a conducting path for the electrical current and has been used previously by other authors [5]. The current was introduced through the top of the domain, and the outer edge of the substrate was grounded. Using the conductivities for aluminium and CFRP, this simulation was run twice to

investigate the effect of substrate conductivity on the plasma dynamics. The resulting density, pressure, and temperature of the lightning plasma after 10 μ s are shown in Figure 1. The density and pressure fields reveal an outward-travelling, cylindrical shock wave, which was also observed in experiments [16]. In the middle of the lightning arc, the pressure and temperature rose due to the Joule heating effect. Far away from the substrate surface, the plasma behaviour was independent of substrate conductivity. At the arc root, however, the plasma dynamics varied. For the aluminium substrate, the arc became narrower near the substrate surface, while for the CFRP substrate, it spread out. Both shapes were also observed experimentally by Sousa Martins [16]. This shows that the present model correctly captures the coupling between substrate conductivity and arc root dynamics.

Figure 2: Pressure and damage within substrate material after 4 μ s of being subjected to electrical current introduced through the top of the domain, with electrical conductivity of CFRP (left) and aluminium (right).

B. Substrate Material Model

To verify the implementation of the substrate material model, a simulation was performed containing only the substrate. The effect of the lightning arc on the substrate was modelled by prescribing a current influx through the top of the domain, which followed a Gaussian profile [3].

$$J_z = -\frac{I}{\pi r_0^2} e^{-\left(\frac{r}{r_0}\right)^2}$$

Here, $r_0 = 2$ mm. Thus, thermal-electric loading of the substrate was accounted for, but pressure loading was neglected. One advantage of using the fully compressible formulation of the problem is that thermal stresses arise naturally when energy is introduced into the material. Thus, no dedicated terms are required to account for thermal expansion. Reflective boundary conditions were applied at the top and bottom of the domain, and the outer edge of the domain was grounded. One simulation was run with the EOS, plasticity model, damage model, and electrical conductivity corresponding to aluminium. A second simulation was run with the same material model, but the electrical conductivity of CFRP. This was done as a proof-of-concept, while a suitable anisotropic material model for CFRP is under development. For both materials, it was assumed that electrical conductivity degrades linearly with damage. The resulting pressure and damage distribution in the substrate after 4 μ s can be seen in Figure 2. No damage occurred in the aluminium substrate, while there was significant damage in the CFRP substrate. This was due to the low conductivity of CFRP, which increased the magnitude of the Joule heating term. A rapid rise in pressure ensued, which eventually led to stresses exceeding the elastic limit of the material. The damage was highest near the top surface where the current was introduced, which resembled the damage distribution found in post-experiment C-scan images [17]. Agreement with experimental damage data is expected to improve when the damage model is tailored to CFRP and includes information on its laminate structure. However, this result shows that the method can capture the effect of electrical conductivity on mechanical damage within a substrate material under lightning test conditions.

C. Coupled Simulation of Plasma and Substrate

Having shown that the model is able to separately capture the plasma dynamics and onset of damage as a function of substrate conductivity, a coupled simulation of the substrate with the lightning plasma was performed. To demonstrate the onset of

damage in this scenario, the yield stress of the substrate material was reduced to 100 MPa. This is because, as opposed to the isolated substrate test in Section V.B, the stress reached in this test was not high enough to exceed the regular yield stress of aluminium. One possible explanation for this is that the reflective boundary conditions in the previous test artificially increased the stress by inhibiting any expansion of the material. Two simulations were run with the conductivities of aluminium and CFRP, respectively. The resulting density, pressure, and damage at 3 μ s can be seen in Figure 3. Much of the same plasma features appeared as in the rigid body case in Section V.A: a radially outward travelling shock wave, a narrow arc root for the aluminium substrate, and a widening arc root for the CFRP substrate. The evolution inside the substrate showed a few differences from Section V.B. Previously, the pressure in the aluminium remained close to atmospheric conditions. In the coupled simulation, however, a peak pressure of around 10 MPa was reached. This was because in this simulation, the substrate not only experienced loading from Joule heating, but also from the high pressure in the plasma arc. The pressure distribution inside the CFRP substrate was also different than in the substrate-only test. Firstly, the high-pressure region was not as concentrated in the centre of the substrate. This could be attributed to the expansion of the plasma arc, which caused the electrical current to flow into the substrate over a wider area. It highlights the importance of the plasma model in finding the correct substrate loading. Secondly, the magnitude of the pressure was much lower than in Section V.B, for reasons discussed previously. The pressure was, however, still an order of magnitude higher than in the aluminium substrate - it exceeded 100 MPa. This shows that in low-conductivity materials, the contribution of Joule heating to overall stress is significantly higher than the contribution of pressure loading. Because of the low pressure, there was no damage in the aluminium substrate. In the CFRP substrate, on the other hand, the substrate was damaged near the outer edge of the arc root, a region with high current density. In the experimental results by Hirano et al. [17], the damage occurred more towards the centre of the arc. However, agreement with experimental results is expected to improve with a more complete model for the properties of CFRP.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, preliminary results were presented for a new approach to the fully coupled simulation of a lightning plasma and a substrate material. It was shown that the model correctly

Figure 3: Density, pressure, and substrate damage 3 μ s after lightning attachment to substrate material with electrical conductivity of CFRP (left) and aluminium (right).

captures the dynamics of the lightning plasma with different substrate conductivities, and the generation of damage within the substrate material was demonstrated when a prescribed current was introduced. Finally, a coupled multi-material simulation was presented where damage occurred due to lightning attachment a low-conductivity substrate. Future work will include improvement of the substrate model by extending the model to anisotropic materials and implementing state-of-the-art failure criteria for CFRP. In this way, a better

quantitative agreement with experimental observations will be achieved and the predictive capability of the model will be improved. Furthermore, the model will be used to study scenarios with material interface separation. This will include the study of breach of containment in fastener configurations and delamination. Finally, multi-layered substrates will be investigated to study the effects of LSP and paint on substrate damage.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to acknowledge the funding support from Boeing Research and Technology (BR&T). We would also like to thank Louisa Michael and Philipp Boettcher for their technical input throughout the project.

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